

Methodological Model for Developing Communicative Competence of Medical University Students Based on Interactive Methods using Authentic Fictional Video Materials

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Abstract. Objective: *To develop and test a methodological model for improving the English communicative competence of medical university students using authentic artistic films.*

Material and Methods: *The study used authentic video materials, specifically the medical TV series "House M.D.," along with a specially developed educational guide. Interactive teaching methods were applied to develop the four components of communicative competence. The study involved conducting classes using these materials and methods, as well as testing to evaluate their effectiveness.*

Results: *The use of authentic artistic films in the learning process significantly improved students' communicative competence. According to the study, the experimental groups showed substantial improvement in material retention compared to the control groups: 62% of students mastered all four aspects (compared to 1.1% in the control group), 34.5% mastered three aspects (compared to 2.3%), 40.7% mastered two aspects (compared to 20.9%), and only 2.8% of the experimental group did not master any aspects (compared to 45.8% in the control group). The only negative result in mastering one aspect (15.8% compared to 29.9%) is still considered positive since most students in the experimental group mastered more aspects and provided their responses. The experiment demonstrated high results in forming discursive, sociolinguistic, and strategic competencies, as well as the ability to adequately choose and use language tools in various situations.*

Conclusion: *The methodological model based on the use of authentic artistic films and interactive teaching methods proved effective in improving the English communicative competence of medical university students. The study results confirm the feasibility of applying this model to achieve high educational goals.*

Key words: *English communicative competence, medical universities, authentic artistic films, interactive learning, methodological model, discursive competence, sociolinguistic competence, strategic competence.*

Introduction

In the modern global community, proficiency in foreign languages is an integral part of the professional competence of future medical specialists. In global theories and practices of English language education, there is a growing demand for carefully selecting the content of language education to meet the communicative needs of medical students in both their daily and professional activities. In the context of the need to update methods and technologies in modern education, the professional-oriented teaching of English in medical universities using authentic film materials is of particular relevance.

In the scientific community, the issue of teaching professional medical English in non-philological universities is a priority direction for improving activities aimed at enhancing the quality of any medical practice. This issue is being studied in major scientific institutions and higher educational establishments around the world, including the University of Edinburgh (UK), the University of Copenhagen (Denmark), Cape Breton University (Canada), Jiangsu University (China), Johns Hopkins School of Medicine (USA), Bukovinian State Medical University (Ukraine), and the experience of Kazakh National Medical University named after S. D. Asfendiyarov (Kazakhstan) and the University of Tokyo (Japan). Studying these experiences helps establish connections aimed at creating and implementing new approaches and methods to effectively solve the problem of teaching medical English.

Research on teaching the language of medicine conducted at Vinnytsia National Medical University named after M.I. Pirogov (Ukraine), I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Russia), and Belarusian State Medical University (Belarus) is dedicated to studying the issues of forming professional competence in future medical specialists, methodological support, and modeling professional speech. Significant attention is given to the study of foreign languages using authentic audio-visual artistic materials in the following universities: North-Western State Medical University named after I.I. Mechnikov (Russia), the University of Birmingham (UK), the University of Zurich (Switzerland), Seoul National University (South Korea), and Heidelberg University (Germany).

A particular requirement for the level of formation of professional-oriented competence of medical university students, including practical skills and abilities in communication in the studied non-native/foreign language, highlights the urgency of the problem of teaching the language of specialty and the search for innovative solutions to improve the quality of training highly qualified medical professionals. After gaining independence, citizens of foreign countries residing in our country, particularly medical specialists, face challenges in effective workplace interaction. Additionally, there is a practical need to develop a comprehensive guide for national medical practitioners on using specialized vocabulary when interacting with colleagues from abroad. Proficiency in communicative skills in medical English opens prospects for medical specialists from CIS countries for internships abroad, publications in leading medical journals indexed in prestigious databases, and participation in international conferences.

Purpose of the study

The objective of this research is to identify innovative methods for developing English communicative competence

Materials and Methods

The study of the methodological model for improving the English communicative competence of medical students through feature films is based on the works of several prominent scholars and educators. Significant contributions to the theory and methodology of foreign language teaching have been made by I.A. Zimnyaya, N.I. Gez, V.I. Ivanova-Tsyganova, A.A. Leontiev, E.I. Passov, Yu.M. Lotman, G.I. Kutuzova, N.D. Galskova, I.L. Bim, T.A. Barabash, L.V. Bankevich, and I.A. Shcherbakova.

A.A. Leontiev, E.I. Passov, and I.L. Bim have extensively illuminated the principles and foundations of communicative competence, which is a key aspect of our research(4). Their works provide a theoretical foundation for developing methodological approaches to teaching English. Contributions by I.A. Zimnyaya, N.I. Gez, and N.D. Galskova have significantly influenced considerations related to the methodology of teaching English as a foreign language, linguocultural studies, and the psychology of the learning process(3). These aspects are crucial for understanding and implementing innovative methodological models in the educational process.

V.I. Ivanova-Tsyganova, Yu.M. Lotman, G.I. Kutuzova, and I.A. Shcherbakova have explored issues of film semiotics and the use of audiovisual tools in teaching. Their research confirms the effectiveness of using feature films for foreign language teaching. T.A. Barabash (1) and L.V.

Bankevich (2) have developed methodological guides on working with feature films, forming the basis for further research and the development of teaching materials within this project.

Among international researchers who have studied the use of films in education are Ismaili M., Kabooha N., Liando S., and Goctu R. Their work focuses on improving speaking and listening skills through film materials. Aliyev A., Albay M., and Kalra R. emphasize the use of authentic films to develop communicative and speech skills. Studies by Jonghak B., Wang P., Nikmah A., Dikilitas K., and others confirm the theoretical contribution of authentic films to pedagogy. Shakir M. and Yaseen N. have published works on vocabulary enhancement, while Auberg A. has demonstrated increased student motivation in second language learning through feature films. Mahmoodi-Shahrebabaki M. has researched the reduction of student anxiety through specific teaching methods(5).

Several researchers, including Khurmuz O.V., Golushko A.P., Zybina O.I., and Permyakova E.K., have dedicated their work to using feature films in foreign language teaching. Their research covers a wide range of aspects, from methodological recommendations to the creation of teaching aids and optimization of the learning process in non-linguistic universities.

This research employs a multi-step methodological approach, including theoretical analysis, diagnostic methods, prognostic methods, pedagogical experiments, and mathematical methods. This comprehensive approach ensures a thorough assessment of the developed methodological model and its impact on the communicative skills of medical students(6).

Theoretical Analysis: Theoretical analysis is a crucial first stage of the research, involving the study and analysis of psychological, pedagogical, and methodological literature. At this stage, the works of leading scholars in communicative competence, foreign language teaching methodology, and the use of audiovisual tools in education were examined. This analysis helped identify the main theoretical and methodological foundations for developing the methodological model and reveal existing approaches and their limitations.

Diagnostic Methods: Diagnostic methods, such as surveys, interviews, and pedagogical observation, were used to obtain initial data on the current level of communicative competence of medical students. Surveys collected quantitative data on students' perceptions of the learning material and their proficiency in English. Interviews with teachers and students provided qualitative data, helping to understand their opinions and experiences in depth. Pedagogical observation allowed for a visual assessment of the learning process and student interactions during classes.

Prognostic Methods: Prognostic methods included experimental evaluation and summarization of students' self-assessments. Experimental evaluation was conducted under controlled pedagogical experiment conditions, where students worked with the developed teaching materials based on feature films. Summarizing self-assessments helped understand how students perceive the proposed methodology as effective and useful for their learning.

Pedagogical Experiment: The key stage of the research was the pedagogical experiment aimed at evaluating the impact of the developed methodological model on the communicative skills of medical students. The experiment included control and experimental groups of students, taught by traditional methods and the developed model, respectively. Regular testing and assessment of practical skills were conducted during the experiment, allowing for an objective measurement of changes in students' communicative competence.

Mathematical Methods: Mathematical methods, including statistical analysis and graphical representation of results, were used to process the obtained data. Statistical data processing identified significant differences between the control and experimental groups and determined the effectiveness of the proposed methodological model. Graphical representation of results provided a visual depiction of the dynamics of changes and allowed for a better understanding of the relationships between different variables.

Results

The experimental research was conducted in three higher medical educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute (hereinafter TashPMI), Samarkand Medical Institute (hereinafter SamMI), and Bukhara Medical Institute (hereinafter BukhMI).

The survey was structured into three sections, covering the following aspects:

General information about the respondents, including their personal interests and opinions.

Assessment of the level of communicative competence in English, including grammatical, discursive, sociolinguistic, and strategic competencies.

Evaluation of knowledge of professional medical terminology in English.

The survey of respondents' personal opinions was conducted using a strategic approach. The first two questions in the survey aimed to identify the students' interest in non-traditional forms of learning, specifically assessing the effectiveness of using authentic films in educational sessions. Positive responses to these questions placed students in the experimental group, while negative responses placed them in the control group. Including a control group was necessary to ensure the reliability and validity of the results.

Subsequent questions did not influence the course of the experiment as the research program had already been developed. However, they helped to gauge students' attitudes towards future activities and confirmed the correctness of the chosen course of action.

When selecting the most productive genre for language learning and a specific film that facilitates the acquisition of medical terminology, the overwhelming majority of respondents expressed a preference for genres related to their future professional field. Therefore, the TV series "House M.D." was chosen as the primary source for learning medical English. The discrepancy in students' opinions regarding the choice of subtitle language when watching the film was then analyzed, dividing them into two groups: those who chose "English only" subtitles and those who preferred "Russian along with English" subtitles. It was concluded that when opting for English-only subtitles, students might not objectively assess their language proficiency and the complexity of authentic medical speech not adapted for non-native speakers. Therefore, it is recommended to use simultaneous subtitle translation to ensure better content comprehension.

The following questions aimed to explore students' individual motivation to participate in the experiment and their readiness to maintain active participation even in the absence of initial positive results. The inclusion of these aspects was intended to identify the connection between a conscious desire to participate and positive learning dynamics, if observed. Additionally, the possible objective reason for the absence of high cognitive activity upon completion of the experiment with low results was considered.

The second block of survey questions was aimed at assessing the four aspects of language proficiency that collectively form communicative competence. Considering that this section poses certain difficulties for students not studying in specialized higher education institutions, it was not expected to receive high results from participants during the initial phase of the experiment. In fact, the possibility of leaving this section of the survey unanswered was anticipated. However, the data obtained from students should manifest in the control part of the experiment, where they encounter similar tasks. If our hypothesis is confirmed, completing these tasks should not pose difficulties.

Awareness and Skills in Applying the Four Aspects of Communicative Competence during the Initial Assessment:

Grammatical Competence: The ability to use correct grammatical structures in English.

Discursive Competence: The ability to produce coherent and cohesive discourse in English.

Sociolinguistic Competence: The ability to appropriately use language in different social contexts.

Strategic Competence: The ability to effectively use communication strategies to overcome language deficiencies and ensure successful interaction.

The initial assessment results provided a baseline for measuring the effectiveness of the developed methodological model and its impact on the communicative skills of medical students.

Table 1

Name of institution Quantity of learned aspects	TashPMI (n=150)	BuxMI(n=106)	SamMI (n=106)	Total (n=354)
4 aspects	-	-	-	-
3 aspects	3	2	2	7
2 aspects	28	22	18	68
1 aspect	34	30	27	91
0 aspect	85	52	51	188

Results

In the "Grammatical Competence" section, the task proposed required the formation of two independent sentences, rich in medical terminology and diverse linguistic structures(7). Initially, it is expected that students would create "simple" sentences with a "Russified" flavor, meaning sentences that are direct translations from Russian to English without considering the specifics of the language and linguistic constructions. In the control group, more complex and substantive language constructs typical of native English speakers were expected when completing the same task.

In analyzing discursive competence, students were asked to compose short dialogues on medical topics. This aligns with E.V. Schumann's definition of discursive competence as the ability to understand and produce logically connected oral or written statements. Interestingly, most participants were able to successfully complete this task even before the experiment began. However, the quality of the material presented varied significantly between the initial and control stages. During the initial stage, students often created dialogues with a low level of communicative complexity. However, during the control survey, many of them demonstrated dialogues characterized by high intellectual complexity, comparable in quality to professionally created dialogues from authentic medical films.

The next section involved assessing sociolinguistic competence, based on N.N. Panaiti's definition, which describes it as an understanding of the sociocultural rules of language and discourse. Students were asked about the differences in speech behavior between Americans and Uzbeks, with the option to respond in their native language. This was done to focus their attention on the meaning rather than the form of the language and to avoid possible language difficulties influencing their responses. In the initial stage, most students lacked sociolinguistic knowledge. However, upon completion of the training, over 70% of students demonstrated a better understanding of sociolinguistic competence, providing detailed responses to this question.

Final Assessment of Awareness and Skills in Applying the Four Aspects of Communicative Competence in Control Groups:

Table 2

Aspect	Initial Stage	Control Stage
Grammatical Competence	Simple sentences with "Russified" elements	Complex, substantive sentences typical of native speakers
Discursive Competence	Low communicative complexity dialogues	High intellectual complexity dialogues, comparable to professional dialogues from authentic medical films

Sociolinguistic Competence	Limited sociolinguistic knowledge	Over 70% demonstrated improved understanding and detailed responses
Strategic Competence	To be assessed (not mentioned in the provided text)	To be assessed (not mentioned in the provided text)

Final assessment of the students' awareness and skills in applying the four aspects of communicative competence in the control groups

Table 2

Name of institution / Quantity of learned aspects	TashPMI (n=75)	BuhMI (n=53)	SamMI (n=49)	Total (n=177)
4 aspects	1	1	0	2
3 aspects	2	1	1	4
2 aspects	15	12	10	37
1 aspect	22	14	17	53
0 aspect	35	25	21	81

Final assessment of the students' awareness and skills in applying the four aspects of communicative competence in the experimental groups

Table 3

Name of institution / Quantity of learned aspects	TashPMI (n=75)	BuhMI (n=53)	SamMI (n=49)	Total (n=177)
4 aspects	5	3	3	11
3 aspects	19	27	15	61
2 aspects	38	14	20	72
1 aspect	11	7	10	28
0 aspect	2	2	1	5

Step 1: Calculation of Proportions

Control Groups:

4 aspects: $2/177 = 0.011$

3 aspects: $4/177 = 0.023$

2 aspects: $37/177 = 0.209$

1 aspect: $53/177 = 0.299$

0 aspects: $81/177 = 0.458$

Experimental Groups:

4 aspects: $11/177 = 0.062$

3 aspects: $61/177 = 0.345$

2 aspects: $72/177 = 0.407$

1 aspect: $28/177 = 0.158$

0 aspects: $5/177 = 0.028$

Step 2: Comparison of Proportions

4 aspects: The experimental groups demonstrated a significantly higher proportion (0.062 vs. 0.011).

3 aspects: The experimental groups also showed a higher proportion (0.345 vs. 0.023).

2 aspects: The experimental groups had a slightly higher proportion (0.407 vs. 0.209).

1 aspect: The experimental groups exhibited a lower proportion (0.158 vs. 0.299), which is considered a positive outcome as the majority of students in the experimental group mastered more aspects.

0 aspects: The experimental groups significantly reduced the proportion of students who did not master any aspects (0.028 vs. 0.458), which is also regarded as a positive outcome.

Discussion

For medical students, mastering grammatical competence is especially crucial, and the use of professionally produced films on medical topics appears appropriate(8). However, considering the significant differences in sentence structure and construction between English and languages like Russian or Uzbek, watching original English films might lead to misunderstandings in learning grammatical rules.

Locally produced films, where the native language is Russian or Uzbek but translated into English, might be more preferable. In such non-original films, sentence structures align with local dialects, providing a clear literal translation and reflecting the grammatical essence of the English language without excessive complexity. In the process of acquiring phonetic aspects of the language at an automatic level, listening to the proper speech of the translator plays a crucial role. This stage allows the recipient, i.e., the language learner, to subconsciously perceive sounds and intonations, forming correct acoustic perception of the language. This form of learning effectively integrates phonetic skills into daily practice, facilitating their effortless acquisition. It is noteworthy that this stage of developing phonetic competence does not require special efforts from the recipient. Conscious effort is minimized here, as phonetic elements of the language are absorbed under the influence of the translator's authentic pronunciations.

The second important aspect is vocabulary expansion through familiarization with commonly used terminology(9). This process occurs naturally during communication and information perception in the target language. Gradually, the recipient begins to recognize, remember, and actively use terms specific to the subject area, contributing to the formation of lexical-semantic competence. Ultimately, with systematic and quality material processing, the number of unfamiliar words decreases over time. This process is reinforced by repetition, communication, and immersion in the language environment, which actively supports the development of linguistic skills. Thus, the effectiveness of phonetic aspect acquisition and vocabulary expansion are interrelated, creating a reliable foundation for successful linguistic interaction.

Regarding the development of sociolinguistic aspects, students acquire the skill to distinguish between the literal and figurative meanings of specific terms, which is an important part of their communicative competence(10). Artistic films have a unique ability to transform emotional, gestural, and facial aspects, as well as ironic rhythm, into visual form. This allows students to better understand and assimilate the cultural norms of the studied language, as well as communication and behavioral standards. Visual representation serves as an illustration of the behavioral models of native speakers in various scenarios, helping students to distinguish between typical and atypical behavior in the context of intercultural communication(11). The cultural features of the studied language directly influence the structure and form of sentences. For example, in English, compared to Russian and Uzbek, there is a predominance of the most polite form of expressing thoughts. These linguistic norms are so ingrained that even in conditions of tense communication, they maintain their syntactic structure. Thus, using artistic films in education allows students not only to master linguistic skills

but also to gain a deeper understanding of cultural contexts, which contributes to the formation of comprehensive communicative competence.

Discourse competence is defined as the set of knowledge and skills necessary for creating and interpreting texts considering their structural patterns and linguistic standards of various discourse genres(12). An important aspect is ensuring the coherence and consistency of content. This competence manifests in practice during oral or written communication, providing messages with an orderly and logical structure. Watching films, especially those specialized for future professional activities, involves complete, logically connected, and everyday actions(13). This represents one of the effective simulations of a real sociolinguistic environment, where the student acts as an observer, analyzing the life context of other individuals. During the film viewing, analysis of the use of foreign lexical units, terminology, linguistic constructions, and non-traditional syntactic structures in the context of the native language takes place.

Films provide an opportunity to see and understand how narratives are structured, how dialogues are constructed, and how cultural and linguistic norms manifest in various situations(14). This facilitates the development of students' skills in discourse analysis and understanding the diversity of communicative acts. During this process, the use of foreign lexical units, terminology, linguistic constructions, and non-traditional syntactic structures is analyzed in the context of the native language. An illustrative example can be found in the TV series "House, M.D.," where each episode presents a logical sequence of events as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Throughout the eight seasons of "House, M.D.," more than 177 cases of diseases, numerous symptoms, treatment recommendations, and various everyday life scenarios are presented. By applying our methodological model in the educational process, students have the opportunity to observe the coherence of the plot, dialogues, and actions that form a holistic unity and give the text meaning. This is a key characteristic of the text and a necessary condition for achieving textual integrity. The coherence of dialogues ensures the logical-semantic, grammatical, and stylistic connection between elements, which is the foundation for plot integrity.

In traditional approaches to English language teaching, developing strategic competence is a challenging task. Mastery of grammatical rules and an extensive vocabulary is not always sufficient for effective communication in real life(15). Problems arise if the speaker encounters an unfamiliar topic or a conversation partner who does not fully comprehend the information being presented. Traditional language teaching methods typically do not include training in strategies for restoring communication after "breakdowns" occur and do not provide authentic dialogues that reflect real language situations(16). In contrast, analyzing artistic films that mimic real-life scenarios offers more suitable conditions for achieving the desired effect. Since the basic principles of strategic competence are largely universal in civilized societies, observing vocabulary, choice of linguistic means, and methods of overcoming speech difficulties in various communication situations becomes clearer for students.

The use of non-verbal means, such as gestures, facial expressions, and postures, has similar interpretations across different cultures(17). For example, a gesture involving a clenched fist with the thumb pointed upwards is interpreted as a symbol of approval in several cultures. Additionally, there is a general normative restriction on direct insults in some countries, highlighting the universality of certain strategies across different cultural contexts. Ultimately, observing linguistic behavior in diverse communication scenarios, as well as analyzing the choice of lexical and linguistic means and methods for overcoming difficulties, serves as a visual and effective method for students to study the language.

Conclusion

The use of authentic materials, such as films, in language learning is always engaging, especially in specialized fields like medicine. The analysis of the presented data highlights several key points. First, the use of authentic films contributes to the formation of the sociocultural aspect of communicative competence. This is due to the vivid depiction of the target language culture through various elements such as speech nuances, gestures, facial expressions, etc. This approach allows students to gain a deeper understanding of context and meanings, which is often unattainable when focusing solely on grammar and vocabulary.

Second, teaching with authentic films is characterized by a communicative-oriented approach, ensuring a denser informational focus. Films enable students to immerse themselves in real-life communication situations and information delivery at the native language level, which promotes more effective language acquisition.

The third aspect concerns teaching methodology. Through the developed methodological model based on the use of authentic films, students practice grammatical skills within the continuous flow of logical events. This intuitive approach allows learners to automatically grasp grammar by focusing on the semantic aspect rather than the language form. Moreover, authentic films enrich students' vocabulary, including professional terminology. Additionally, using video clips from the series "House, M.D." helps students improve pronunciation and immerse themselves in medical terminology, overcoming the challenges of professionally-oriented texts. The visual and emotional accompaniment of these clips aids in better information retention and vocabulary activation.

Finally, the study results confirm the effectiveness of using authentic films in teaching medical English. Students demonstrated a high level of discursive and sociolinguistic competence, the ability to adequately select language forms and means of communication in various situations. Skills in using compensatory strategies when faced with a lack of knowledge or vocabulary were also noted. Thus, the use of authentic films, such as "House, M.D.," in teaching medical English not only enhances students' linguistic development but also enriches their cultural and professional experience, making this teaching method highly effective and appealing.

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